

Core Design Optimization of eVinci Commercial Microreactor

Nicolas E. Stauff^{1*}, Kyle Ramey¹, William Walters², Fausto Franceschini³

¹ Argonne National Laboratory, Lemont, IL, USA;

² Westinghouse Electric Company, Pittsburgh, PA, USA;

³ Westinghouse Mangiarotti, Italy;

*nstauff@anl.gov

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ABSTRACT

A formal and automated workflow was developed jointly by Argonne National Laboratory and Westinghouse for multi-objective neutronic optimization of Westinghouse's 15 MWt eVinci microreactor. The eVinci core employs HALEU TRISO fuel embedded in graphite with sodium heat-pipe heat removal, reactivity control via rotating drums and shutdown rods, and distributed burnable absorbers. The workflow, implemented with WATTS, orchestrates Serpent-2.2 physics calculations and Dakota's multi-objective genetic algorithm. The optimization intends to maximize discharge burnup and minimize power peaking factors while meeting shutdown margins throughout at least 8 equivalent full power years of operation. Eight design variables spanning burnable absorber axial/radial multipliers and radii, TRISO packing fraction radial multipliers, fuel block radius, and axial core length are optimized in two steps to reduce dimensionality. Each step converged in fewer than 200 simulations, with 75% (step 1) and 40% (step 2) of cases satisfying constraints. Relative to a manually optimized reference, the best solution increases discharge burnup by ~6%, sustains lower peaking, meets shutdown margins, and achieves the 8 EFPY target with ~11% lower fuel inventory than the reference solution. The framework developed and exercised in this work enables rapid design iterations that reduces manual effort and error risk, enabling engineers to focus on strategic design decisions.

Keywords: Microreactor, Optimization, WATTS, eVinci, Serpent

1. INTRODUCTION

The eVinci™ microreactor is being developed by Westinghouse Electric Company for a wide range of decentralized remote applications [1]. This reactor design displays a very compact core layout for transportability with thermal power of 15 MW and targeted lifetime of at least 8 equivalent full power years (EFPY). The eVinci concept employs TRISO fuel (with 19.95at% HALEU enrichment) in graphite structure matrix, and the power is extracted through sodium heat-pipes. Its reactivity is controlled by 18 rotating drums located in the radial reflector, and by 24 shutdown rods used during transportation and for secondary shutdown. The eVinci reactor uses burnable absorbent (BA) in different fuel and central reflector assemblies to reduce the excess reactivity and optimize the power distribution. The radial layout of the eVinci design is shown in *Figure 1*. It uses two rings of central reflector assemblies, five rings of fuel assemblies, surrounded by graphite reflector blocks in which the control drums are located.

To achieve an optimal combination of key attributes, such as safety, sustainability, and economic competitiveness for the commercial version of eVinci, Westinghouse and Argonne National Laboratory (ANL) partnered in completing a core design optimization. ANL has acquired wide experience in

advanced nuclear reactor core design optimization that was applied to ABTR [2], to the Holos microreactors [3][4], and to an LFR [5]. A reference eVinci design that was manually optimized is used as the starting point of this analysis. An initial core design optimization was completed in this work that focuses on a limited number of design parameters to develop and demonstrate optimization workflow. Such analysis will be extended in the future to support economic optimization of the eVinci core for commercialization.

Figure 1. Radial layout of the eVinci core

2. METHODOLOGY DESCRIPTION

2.1. Tools Description

The simulation workflow automated in this work for eVinci design characterization and optimization is illustrated in *Figure 2*. WATTS (Workflow and Template Toolkit for Simulation) [6] is used to connect calculation steps together with required pre/post-processing capabilities into a combined Python script. WATTS is a generic open-source workflow management tool developed at ANL.

The current workflow considers 4 neutronic steps used to characterize the performance of the eVinci core. Serpent-2.2 [7] continuous-energy Monte Carlo reactor physics burnup calculation code is used for eVinci modeling, relying on the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library [8]. Each simulation employs 10,000 histories (5,000 during depletion) and 300 active cycles. The volume calculation considers 5×10^9 histories and control drums are modeled fully withdrawn during depletion. Fuel was depleted using five axial subdivisions at fuel compact level (37 fuel compacts per fuel assembly). Despite resulting in relatively large uncertainties (50pcm on k_{eff}), those options provide reasonable accuracy on core lifetime and power peaking parameters of interest with a computing cost compatible with running many simulations (~25 evaluations per day) for optimization analysis on ANL mid-size clusters (120 CPU). Following the optimization analysis, higher fidelity simulations are completed on the most suitable candidates to refine performance estimates.

The Dakota software [9] maintained by Sandia National Laboratory is an uncertainty quantification and optimization toolkit with over 20 years of development. Dakota provides advanced mathematical

methods to vary a code's input parameters and analyze the output results, enabling multi-objective optimization and uncertainty quantification analysis.

Figure 2. Automated Simulation Workflow of the eVinci Core.

2.2. Optimization Problem Definition

This section describes the optimization problem that was defined and resolved using DAKOTA.

- **Objective functions** - three different objectives were attempted to be optimized at the same time:
 - minimization of radial power peaking (MRPP) - informs on peak heat removal of the heat-pipe
 - minimization of the time-integrated power peaking (MTIPP) - axial and radial - informs on peak fuel temperature
 - maximization of discharge burnup (burnup) - informs on core economics since fuel cost is expected to be significant cost driver of this reactor

Those three objective functions are selected in a neutronic-only workflow to improve safety and economics performance of the core. Including the safety and economics modeling within such workflow is considered for future work.

- **Variables** – eight different design variables were defined, as listed in *Table I*. The first four parameters are multipliers to reference values of burnable absorbent concentration and radius (of B₄C diluted in graphite), while the four last parameters are TRISO packing fraction and dimension parameters for fuel block radius, and axial core length. This set of parameters was identified as needing further evaluation, and because of their simplicity to parameterize in the eVinci model. Future work will consider a wider range of geometric parameters. These eight parameters will be considered in two different optimization steps, as further explained later. The high/low range of the variables was determined from expert judgement and testing.
- **Workflow** - four different Serpent calculations are automated as follows:
 - 1- Volume calculation to estimate stochastically the volume of different regions in Serpent for depletion calculations.

- 2- The benchmark concentration of BA is tuned (using simple root scalar optimization method) at BOL to target k-eff of 1.01 (at Xenon equilibrium). The different axial/radial concentrations are then derived from each benchmark BA concentration through the different BA multipliers listed in *Table I*.
- 3- Depletion calculations are performed over 9 years. At this step, one estimates the core lifetime, the maximum radial power peaking (MRPP, calculated at any time during irradiation), the maximum time-integrated power peaking (MTIPP), and the discharge burnup at end of life (when k-eff becomes sub-critical).
- 4- A series of branching calculations are completed at BOL and at 7 years (observed typical peak of reactivity, as shown later) to estimate different shutdown margins constraints described next.

Table I. Design variables and ranges.

ID	Description	Low	High	Num Points
Optimization Step #1				
BAA	BA - axial multiplier	0.5	0.8	7
BAR	BA - radial multiplier	0.7	1.0	7
BARF	BA radius multiplier - fuel region	0.78	1.3	10
BARC	BA radius multiplier - central region	0.8	1.0	5
Optimization Step #2				
RC	Radius of fuel block - multiplier	0.88	1.19	6
PF1	packing fraction - radial multiplier #1	1.05	1.25	21
PF2	packing fraction - radial multiplier #2	1.10	1.20	11
FL	Axial core length - multiplier	0.94	1.06	4

- **Constraints** – the following constraints are considered to verify viability of the different core options: 1) core lifetime (with k-eff > 1.0) needs to be larger than 8 EFPY; and 2) the following shutdown margins are considered:
 - (ADIM1) k-eff < 0.97 with all drums in (minus one) at nominal temperature conditions (BOL and 7yr)
 - (ARIM1) k-eff < 0.97 with all rods in (minus one) at nominal temperature conditions (BOL and 7yr)
- **Optimization steps** – The current list of variables and space resolutions has about 14 million solutions, which would be too time-consuming for the optimization solver to properly investigate. Consequently, the optimization problem was split into two steps:
 - 1- optimizing the different BA axial/radial concentrations – this step uses as a starting point the reference eVinci model that was parameterized.
 - 2- optimizing the different fuel/BA radius and lengths – this step uses as a starting point the selected optimum solution from step #1.

The core optimization is performed with a multi-objective genetic algorithm (MOGA) and direct physics simulations. MOGA is used based on extensive experience applied at ANL on various

previous core design optimization projects. Each optimization step starts with a population of 30 core configurations selected using random sampling.

- **Optimization result selection** – Selecting the best result from a three-objective function optimization is not straightforward. A simple normalized distance calculation is used to estimate how well a solution performs relative to the maximum performance observed on all three objective functions (and similar weight associated with each performance).

3. RESULTS FOR EVINCI DESIGN ANALYSIS

3.1. Optimization Results

The results of the optimization analysis are shown in *Figure 3* for step #1 and *Figure 4* for step #2. Each step converges within less than 200 simulations, with 75% of cases passing all constraints for step #1 and 40% for step #2.

Figure 3. Performance results observed for each simulation of optimization Step#1.

Figure 4. Performance results observed for each simulation of optimization Step#2.

The results of Step #1 shown in *Figure 3* are spread across a large range of radial power peaking since the radial optimization of the burnable poisons and packing fractions are varied. There are only incremental improvements observed on the optimum solution selected, with small reduction of the two power peaking criteria, at the expense of a small reduction of burnup (about 1%).

The results of Step #2 in *Figure 4* do show a wider range of potential performance improvements can be achieved both in burnup and power peaking metrics. The optimum solution does show more significant increase in burnup (about 6%), while maintaining the power peaking performance obtained in previous step.

The main core design parameters varied, and core performance considered are shown in *Table II*. The starting point obtained from manual optimization was found to be fairly close to the optimum solution. Through this 2-step optimization approach, one could identify a more performing solution. The main parameters varied are the BA axial/radial concentrations and PF fractions in different core regions. This enabled notable improvements in power peaking parameters and burnup. The different solutions are within the ranges set for the variables – meaning that extending the ranges for these variables may not be necessary. Through this optimization, the eVinci core designed meets all shutdown constraints while reaching 8 EFPY lifetime with a 11% reduced fuel inventory and 6% increased burnup. The optimization algorithm does converge to the minimum lifetime allowed in order to minimize the fuel inventory.

Table II. Design parameters and performance of Optimum solutions.

	Ref. (starting point)	Opt. (Step #1)	Opt. (Step#2)
Design parameters			
(BAA) BA axial multiplier	0.7	0.55	0.55
(BAR) BA radial multiplier	0.75	0.7	0.7
(BARF) BA radius multiplier - fuel region [cm]	Ref.	0.91	0.91
(BARC) BA radius multiplier - central region	1	0.85	0.85
(RC) Radius of fuel block - multiplier	Ref.	Ref.	0.94
(PF1) packing fraction - radial multiplier #1	1.15	1.15	1.07
(PF2) packing fraction - radial multiplier #2	1.1	1.1	1.12
(FL) Axial core length - multiplier	Ref.	Ref.	1.0
Core Performance			
Fuel mass reduction factor	Ref.	Ref.	0.89
Core lifetime [year]	8.43	8.35	8.01
Discharged burnup improvement (BU _p /BU _p [starting point])	Ref.	0.99	1.06
(MRPP) Max. radial power peaking	1.585	1.545	1.517
(MTIPP) Max. time-integrated power peaking	1.611	1.555	1.564
(ADIM1) K-eff - all drums in minus one – BOL	0.914	0.917	0.917
(ADIM1) K-eff - all drums in minus one – 7yr	0.956	0.946	0.955
(ARIM1) K-eff - all rods in minus one – BOL	0.894	0.893	0.890
(ARIM1) K-eff - all rods in minus one – 7yr	0.853	0.850	0.847

Figure 5. Reactivity swing for optimum core solutions.

The burnup reactivity swing of the different core solutions is shown in *Figure 5*. The peak excess reactivity is obtained at BOL and drops quickly due to fission product poisoning, before stabilizing around 1.005. In some cases, k -eff increases back at around 7 EFPY when most of the burnable poisons are consumed, which is where the shutdown margins can be especially challenging to meet.

Leveraging a total of 188 successful simulations (where all constraints are met) performed in optimization steps #1 and #2, one could estimate the correlation coefficients between input and outputs as shown in *Table III*. This analysis helps identify which parameter has little impact on results (BARC - central BA radius multipliers) and could potentially be removed from subsequent optimization analyses. All other parameters show some level of weak ($abs > 0.4$) or strong ($abs > 0.8$) positive or negative correlations with the core performance and would need to be maintained in future analyses.

Table III. Pearson correlations on non-failing optimization solutions.

	BAA	BAR	BARF	BARC	RC	PF1	PF2	FL
Burnup	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1	-0.8	-0.3	-0.2	0.0
MRPP	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.0	-0.6	-0.6	0.3
MTIPP	0.2	0.5	0.7	-0.1	0.1	-0.2	-0.4	0.3
Lifetime	0.1	0.4	0.0	0.3	0.3	-0.2	-0.5	0.6
ADIM1-BOL	-0.4	0.1	0.5	-0.2	-0.1	-0.2	0.0	0.0
ADIM1-7YR	0.3	0.6	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.6	0.5
ARIM1-BOL	0.2	-0.4	-0.3	0.0	0.5	0.2	0.2	-0.1
ADIM1-7YR	0.3	0.6	0.6	0.0	0.2	0.0	-0.6	0.5

4. CONCLUSIONS

A formal, automated workflow was developed to support the design and optimization of the Westinghouse eVinci core. The framework integrates a comprehensive suite of reactor-physics analyses and is coupled to DAKOTA to perform multi-objective optimization that maximizes burnup

and minimizes power peaking while satisfying shutdown margin and core lifetime constraints. By standardizing data flow and automating routine evaluations, the approach reduces manual effort and error risk, enabling engineers to focus on strategic design decisions after an initial investment in workflow development. Applied to eVinci, the optimization identified multiple viable core configurations that informed Westinghouse design choices. Future work will extend the optimization space to additional geometric parameters—such as assembly pitch and the number and placement of control drums and shutdown rods—which will require more sophisticated model parameterization but offer greater potential for performance gains.

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